

Removal of an anionic dye, Orange G from aqueous solutions by adsorption on unmodified sheesham (*Dalbergia sisso*) saw dust

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Abstract : Removal of an anionic dye, Orange G from its aqueous solutions by adsorption on raw (unmodified) saw dust was investigated. The effect of contact time and initial concentration, temperature, and pH on the removal of the selected dye was studied. Equilibrium was achieved in 50 min. A higher removal (%) was achieved in lower concentration ranges. A maximum removal of the dye (63.2%) was achieved at pH 1.0. The process of dye removal follows pseudo-second order kinetics and the value of rate constant was found to be 5.99 min.g/mg at 298 K. The equilibrium modeling of the adsorption process was carried out and the data fitted better in Freundlich isotherm model. The negative values of Gibb's free energy (ΔG^0) showed spontaneity of the adsorption process. The negative value of enthalpy change (ΔH^0) confirmed the exothermic nature of the process. The process can be recommended for the removal of dye from coloured effluents.

Keywords : Adsorption, Orange G dye, saw dust, isotherm, kinetics.

Introduction

Effluents from the industries like textile, dying, printing, cosmetics, food coloring and papermaking are responsible for imparting colour to the receiving sources¹. Out of these industries, textile, and pulp and paper industries consume large amount of different dyes which in turn find a way to water resources and are responsible for many harmful effects² on fauna, flora and humans. Coloured water is also aesthetically unpleasant and unacceptable. A number of dyes are very toxic and display carcinogenic and mutagenic effects on aquatic biota and human being³. Because of distinct nature, colour of water can be recognized at minute levels of 1.0 mg L⁻¹. Colour restricts penetration of solar radiations and retards photosynthesis which results in increase of COD and BOD levels of aquatic sources. Dyes are also reported^{4,5} to possess a tendency to chelate metal ions resulting in micro-toxicity to aquatic fauna and flora.

Most of the dyes are stable to photo-degradation, and bio-degradation^{6,7}. The physicochemical and biological techniques namely membrane filtration, coagulation, ion exchange, adsorption, chemical reduction, etc.⁸⁻¹⁰ have been regularly employed for the treatment of coloured effluents.

However, all these techniques have several merits and demerits. Either they are cost intensive or pose problems of maintenance. These problems make these methods cost intensive and many times ineffective for treatment of wide range of coloured wastewaters.

The adsorption process is well known for its simple design and easy operation. It is inexpensive as compared with other physical and chemical processes. Adsorption technique has been used effectively for the removal of dye from waste water^{11,12}. Activated carbon is a widely used adsorbent for the treatment of industrial waste water containing colours and dyes¹³⁻¹⁵. Studies have been reported using various adsorbents such as chitin¹⁵, clay¹⁶, modified silica gel¹⁷ and zeolite¹⁸ for treatment of waste waters. High cost of activated carbon has attracted scientists world over to search for its alternatives and they have tried inexpensive and bio-waste materials^{19,20} for the removal of dyes from coloured effluents. Orange G is a toxic dye with many after effects on human beings and has applications in a large number of industries. An exposure to Orange G has been reported to cause vomiting, dizziness, cyanosis, increased blood pressure and jaundice in humans²¹. The molecular structure of the dye has been depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The molecular structure of dye Orange G.

In the present study raw (unmodified) saw dust of sheesham has been used as an adsorbent for the removal of Orange G from the aqueous solutions. The authors have conducted a literature survey and can confidently say that so far no work has been reported on application of non modified sheesham saw dust for the removal of Orange G from aqueous solutions. Saw dust is a by-product of timber industry and is available in plenty in all parts of the world. It has no or very less economic value. The primary constituents of saw dust are lignin, cellulose and hemicelluloses. The aim of the present study was to determine the optimum conditions for the removal of Orange G from its aqueous solutions. The effect of various important parameters like initial concentration and contact time, pH, and temperature on the removal of the dye has been studied. Kinetic, equilibrium, and thermodynamic studies of the process of removal have also been discussed.

Results and discussion

Surface characterization of adsorbent :

Surface morphology of the raw saw dust was deciphered by scanning electron microscopy and the SEM of the saw dust sample at higher magnification have been given in Fig. 2. The saw dust particles were mostly irregular in shape and were porous. Raw saw dust is characterized by a highly oriented structure in form of filament filled with material that confers the anisotropic character to the saw dust. Chemical composition of the adsorbent analysed through EDS which displayed that major components of the adsorbent are C (45.52%, wt) and O (30.65%, wt) as major components and Ca (0.61%, wt), Cu (2.39%, wt) Zn (1.80%, wt) as minor components.

FTIR analysis :

The IR spectra of saw dust were measured on a Fou-

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrograph of raw saw dust.

rier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer (ABB-FTLA 2000) to elucidate the functional group present on the saw dust (Fig. 3). For measuring IR spectra, pellets were made by using KBr and saw dust in ratio of 100 : 1. The IR spectra were recorded within the range of 500–6000 cm^{-1} .

The saw dust exhibited O–H stretching band on spectrum in the range of 3200–3400 cm^{-1} . A greater number of OH groups on the glucose units of the cellulose polymers broaden the peak. The peak at 1050–1610 cm^{-1} was assigned to the C=O bonds. The absorption bands at 2928.47 and 2880.23 cm^{-1} are due to contribution from C–H stretching. These medium stretching bands show presence of vinyl and methyl groups. Major band between 500 and 600 denotes the C–X group.

Zero point charge of the adsorbent :

The zero point charge, pH_{zpc} , of raw saw dust was determined by titration method and was found to be 7.29. At a pH of solution below the pH_{zpc} of the adsorbent, the surface of saw dust is negatively charged and can attract cations from the solution; and when solution $\text{pH} < \text{pH}_{\text{zpc}}$, the surface of saw dust is positively charged and attractive to anions¹⁹. In the present studies, a low pH was favorable for adsorption of the anionic dye (Orange G) by saw dust. As pH of the system decreased, the number of negatively charged adsorbent sites decreased and number of positively charged surface sites increased, which favors the adsorption of negatively charged dye anions due to electrostatic attraction. Also lower adsorption of Orange G at basic pH is due to the presence of excess OH^- ions competing with dye for adsorption sites.

Fig. 3. Infrared spectra of saw dust.

Effect of contact time and initial concentration of the dye on removal :

Initial concentration of adsorbate is an important parameter and affects the removal process significantly. It has been reported that the removal (%) of the dye is higher in low concentration ranges whereas the fractional removal is always higher in higher ranges of concentration¹². The adsorption capacity at equilibrium (q_e) increased from 0.03 to 0.1 mg/g by raw saw dust with increase in initial concentrations from 2.5 to 10 mg/L at 298 K and pH 2.0. However, the percentage of the dye adsorbed decreases from 24 to 20 by raw saw dust by increasing concentration of dye from 2.5 to 10 mg/L. This might be due to lack of available active sites on the adsorbent surface compared to the relatively large number of active sites required for the binding of high initial concentration of dye molecules. It is clear from the experimental data that removal of dye is rapid in initial stages, goes on decreasing with time and becomes constant at equilibrium²² viz. 50 min.

Effect of pH :

pH of the solution considered to be one of the most important parameter for the adsorption process. In many cases, the process of removal can be significantly controlled by control of pH. It is reported that the change of pH affects the adsorptive process through dissociation of

functional groups on the adsorbent and adsorbate²¹. pH also controls the degree of ionization and affects speciation of the species in solution. In the present studies the removal of Orange G dye by saw dust was studied at pH values of 1, 2 and 4 respectively. A maximum removal (63.2%) of the dye was achieved at pH 1 and it decreased with increase in the pH value (Fig. 4). The uptake of Orange G increased from 8 to 36% with a decrease of pH from 4 to 1, at 25 °C, 120 rpm, and at an initial concentration 2.5 mg/L of the dye.

Effect of temperature :

Temperature is a highly significant parameter as it affects the process of removal of the pollutant species significantly. Thermodynamic parameters, like heat of adsorption and energy of activation play an important role in predicting the adsorption behavior as both are strongly dependent on temperature. Temperature rise significantly affects the solubility and chemical potential of the adsorbate. It has been reported that if solubility of the adsorbate increases with increase in temperature, then chemical potential decreases and both of these effects work in the same direction, causing a decrease in adsorption. If temperature has reverse effect on the solubility then both the said effects will act in the opposite direction and adsorption may increase or decrease depending upon the predominant factor¹⁵.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on removal of Orange G dye (2.5 mg/L concentration) by adsorption on raw saw dust.

In the present experiment the rates of removal at three different temperatures (25, 35 and 45 °C) have been observed. The rate of dye uptake increases noticeably from 20.8 to 24.5% with decreasing temperature from 45 to 25 °C with 1 g/50 ml dose in 50 min at the attainment of equilibrium from 2.5 mg/L of dye solution. The decrease in adsorption capacity of saw dust with increase of temperature indicates an exothermic process. The decrease in adsorption with temperature may be attributed to either decrease in active sites over surface of adsorbent available for adsorption or solvation of the adsorbing species and the increase in the thickness of the boundary layer surrounding the adsorbent with temperature, so that the mass transfer resistance of adsorbate in the boundary layer increases.

Adsorption kinetics for the removal of dye :

Kinetics is another important aspect in evaluation of sorption as a unit operation. Kinetic data is fitted in the known models to decipher kinetics of the process. This exercise subsequently helps in understanding the mechanism of the process of removal and potential rate controlling steps. The pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order kinetic models were used to explore the kinetics of the process of removal of Orange G by raw saw dust.

Pseudo-first order model :

The kinetic studies for the removal of Orange G were undertaken by fitting the kinetic data in linearized form of Lagergren's equation²⁶ :

$$\log (q_e - q) = \log q_e - \left(\frac{K_{ad}}{2.303} \right) \cdot t \quad (1)$$

where q_e and q (both in mg/g) are amounts of Orange G adsorbed at equilibrium and at any time, respectively, and K_{ad} (min^{-1}) is the rate constant of adsorption. Graphs of the figure ' $\log (q_e - q)$ vs t ' are straight and confirm that the process of removal is governed by first order kinetics. The values of first order rate constant were determined by slopes of the straight line plots are presented in Table 1. The values of the rate constant were found to be decreased from $9.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ to $4.9 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ with increase of temperature from 298 to 318 K.

Pseudo-second order model :

The pseudo-second order kinetic equation is based on

Table 1. Kinetic parameters for the removal of Orange G by adsorption on raw saw dust at different temperatures

Pseudo-first order :					
Temp. (K)	$q_{e, \text{Expt.}}$ (mg/g)	$q_{e, \text{Calcd.}}$ (mg/g)	k_{ad} (1/min)	R^2	
298	0.031	0.024	9.5×10^{-2}	0.967	
308	0.029	0.017	6.8×10^{-2}	0.965	
318	0.028	0.014	4.9×10^{-2}	0.944	
Pseudo-second order :					
Temp. (K)	$q_{e, \text{Expt.}}$ (mg/g)	$q_{e, \text{Calcd.}}$ (mg/g)	k_2 (min g/mg)	h (min mg/g)	R^2
298	0.031	0.030	5.99	0.167	0.998
308	0.029	0.028	5.49	0.1819	0.995
318	0.028	0.026	4.20	0.238	0.995

the sorption capacity of the solid phase. The following linearized form of the pseudo-second order equation²⁷ was used in the present studies :

$$t/q_t = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + 1/q_e t \quad (2)$$

where, k_2 and q_e values were determined from the slope and intercepts of the linear plots of t/q_t against t (Fig. 5), respectively and are presented in Table 2. It is clear from the values reported in this table that the calculated q_e values were very close to that of experimentally obtained q_e and the values of correlation coefficients (R^2) were closer to unity. This confirmed that the adsorption of the dye on saw dust followed pseudo-second order kinetics better.

The kinetic data was fitted to both the first order and pseudo-second order kinetic equations and it was observed that the data fits both the kinetic equations. This has been a regular practice also and has been reported by many scientific workers^{10,11,13,14}. This is versatility of the process of removal in the present system.

Adsorption isotherm :

The analysis of equilibrium data to construct adsorption isotherms is significant for designing the adsorption systems. Adsorption isotherms express the mathematical relationship between the quantity of adsorbate and equilibrium concentration of adsorbate remaining in the solution at a constant temperature. Equilibrium modeling for

Fig. 5. Pseudo-second order plot for the adsorption of Orange G on raw saw dust at different temperatures.

Table 2. Values of Langmuir and Freundlich constants for the removal of Orange G by adsorption on raw saw dust

Langmuir's constants					
Temp. (K)	Q_0 (mg/g)	a_L (L/mg)	K_L (L/g)	R_L	R^2
298	0.2636	0.155	0.03928	0.392	0.7792
308	0.2476	0.175	0.0333	0.362	0.8797
318	0.233	0.119	0.02662	0.456	0.9511
Freundlich constants					
Temp. (K)	K_f (mg/g (L/mg))	$1/n$	R^2		
298	0.1724	0.155	0.9997		
308	0.1651	0.175	0.9998		
318	0.1609	0.119	0.9977		

the process of removal of Orange G by adsorption on raw saw dust was carried out by Langmuir's and Freundlich's adsorption isotherm model.

Langmuir isotherm model :

The Langmuir adsorption isotherm model is based on the assumption that during the process of removal, the adsorbent surface is covered by a monolayer of the adsorbate species. The Langmuir isotherm also assumes that maximum adsorption corresponds to a saturated monolayer of solute molecules on the adsorbent surface, and that the energy of adsorption is constant. For the present studies, the linearized form of expression of Langmuir model was used²⁴ :

$$C_e/q_e = 1/K_L + a_L C_e/K_L \quad (3)$$

where C_e (mg L^{-1}), q_e (mg g^{-1}) are the concentrations of adsorbate and amount of adsorbate adsorbed at equilibrium, respectively. The constant K_L (L/g) is the Langmuir equilibrium constant and the K_L/a_L gives the theoretical monolayer saturation capacity, Q_0 .

The equilibrium data was plotted for ' C_e/q_e vs C_e '. The values of Q^0 and a_L , the two constants were calculated from the slopes and intercepts of the figure (Figure not shown) and the values are given in Table 2. It is evident from the Table 2 that with the increase in temperature monolayer adsorption capacity (Q^0) values decreases from 0.26 to 0.23 mg/g . The decreasing values of Q^0 with increasing temperature clearly suggest that the ongoing adsorption process is exothermic in nature.

Calculation of separation factor :

For Langmuir isotherm, a dimensionless separation factor can be expressed by following equation²³ :

$$R_L = 1/(1 + a_L C_0) \quad (4)$$

where C_0 , initial solute concentration (mg L^{-1}) and a_L (L/mg) is the Langmuir constant related to the energy of adsorption. The dimensionless constant separation factor, R_L is used to test whether the adsorption is favorable or not. The values of R_L indicates the type of the isotherm to be either unfavorable ($R_L > 1$), linear ($R_L = 1$), favorable ($0 < R_L < 1$) or irreversible ($R_L = 0$). At all temperatures R_L values have been found to be less

than unity given in Table 2, thereby indicating favourable process for the adsorbent.

Freundlich isotherm :

Adsorption data for the dye on raw saw dust was also fitted to the linear form of Freundlich isotherm²⁴ :

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + 1/n \log C_e \quad (5)$$

where K_f (mg g^{-1}) is the Freundlich constant and n (g/L) is the Freundlich exponent. The equilibrium data was plotted for $\log q_e$ versus $\log C_e$ enables the constant K_f and exponent n to be determined q_e is the amount adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbate, C_e the equilibrium concentration, and $1/n$ and K_f are constants. The constant K_f is related to the degree of adsorption, n provides the tentative estimation of the intensity of the adsorption. The Freundlich isotherm describing Orange G adsorption by raw saw dust has been illustrated in Fig. 6. The values of the Freundlich constants were calculated from the linear portions of the graph. The values of these constants are given in Table 2. The values of the exponent $1/n$ were in the range of 0 to 1, indicating favourable adsorption at all temperatures tested. The values of K_f decreased on increasing temperature thereby indicating that interaction of dye-adsorbent decreases at higher temperature.

Calculation of thermodynamic parameters :

The equilibrium constant K have been calculated from the relations¹⁵ :

$$K = C_e/q_e \quad (6)$$

Fig. 6. Freundlich isotherm for adsorption of Orange G onto raw saw dust at three different temperatures.

where, C_e is the residual adsorbate concentration in solution at equilibrium (mg/L) and q_e is amount of dye adsorbed at equilibrium (mg/g). The values of Gibbs free energy for the adsorption at different temperatures were calculated using following expression¹⁵ :

$$\Delta G^0 = -RT \ln K \quad (7)$$

where, ΔG^0 is standard Gibbs free energy change, R is the universal gas constant and T is absolute temperature (K). The values of standard free energy change (ΔH^0) and the standard entropy change (ΔS^0) using following equations¹⁵ :

$$\Delta G^0 = \Delta H^0 - T\Delta S^0 \quad (8)$$

From eqs. (6) and (7), we obtained :

$$\ln K = -\Delta H^0/RT + \Delta S^0/R \quad (9)$$

The experiments were carried out at three different temperatures 298, 308 and 318 K. It was observed that the values of equilibrium constant, K , decreased with increase in temperature and that shows the exothermic nature of the adsorption (Fig. 7). Hence, from the slope and intercept of plot $\ln K$ vs $1/T$, the value of ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 were obtained. Values of all thermodynamic parameters were

Fig. 7. Plot of $\ln K$ vs $1/T$ for the adsorption of Orange G on to saw dust at three different temperatures.

given in Table 3.

The feasibility of the process is shown by negative values of free energy in Table 3. The decrease in value of free energy with increase in temperature suggests that the process of removal becomes more spontaneous at increasing temperatures and adsorption is favoured at the lower

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of Orange G dye by saw dust

Temp. (T) (K)	Standard Gibbs free energy change ΔG^0 (kJ/mol)	Standard enthalpy change ΔH^0 (kJ/mol)	Standard entropy change ΔS^0 (J/mol K)
298	-10.26		
308	-10.83	-7.65	59.71
318	-11.42		

temperature. The exothermic nature of the process is further confirmed by the negative value of enthalpy. The positive value of entropy suggests that there is increased in randomness after the adsorption of Orange G on raw saw dust.

Conclusions :

Present work reveals that the non toxic and abundantly available adsorbent, sheesham raw saw dust is capable of effectively removing the toxic dye Orange G from aqueous solutions. Adsorption was influenced by various parameters such as initial concentration, temperature and pH. Removal efficiency of the dye decreased with the rise of temperature confirming the exothermic nature of the process. The maximum uptake of dye takes place at pH 1.0. Kinetic and equilibrium studies revealed that unmodified saw dust can be effectively employed for removal of Orange G from aqueous solutions. The adsorption kinetics followed pseudo-second order kinetics. Equilibrium data fits better the Freundlich isotherm model suggesting the heterogenous adsorption surface. The negative values of ΔG^0 suggested that the adsorption was spontaneous in nature. The negative value of ΔH^0 and positive value of ΔS^0 indicated exothermic adsorption process and increased randomness at surface-solution interface, respectively.

Experimental

Materials :

The dye, Orange G :

The dye, Orange G, selected for the present system was procured from Merck India (P.) Limited, Mumbai. The chemical structure of Orange G dye is listed in Fig. 1. Orange G obtained from E. Merck (Mumbai, India) having 99.0% purity was used for the preparation dye solution without further purification.

Saw dust :

The saw dust of sheesham was collected from a local furniture factory from Allahabad. It washed several times with distilled water to remove impurities. The cleaned saw dust was oven dried completely at 110 °C, cooled and sieved to 45–150 µm and was used without further treatment.

Instruments :

SEM (Jeol, Japan), FTIR (Varian 1600 FT-IR Scimitar Series), Orbital Shaker (Narang Scientific Works, New Delhi, India), pH meter (Orion), UV-Vis double beam spectrophotometer (Systronics 2203) were used in this work.

Determination of pH_{zpc} :

For experimental determination of pH_{zpc} of the adsorbent, 0.01 M NaCl was prepared and its pH was adjusted in the range between 2 to 12 by using NaOH or HCl. Then 50 ml of 0.01 M NaCl was taken in 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask and 0.5 g of unmodified saw dust was added in flask containing 0.01 M NaCl solution of different pH. These flasks were then kept for 48 h and after that pH of the solutions was measured by using pH meter. Graphs were then plotted between pH_{final} vs $pH_{initial}$. Where curve of pH_{final} vs $pH_{initial}$ intersect each other that point was recorded as pH_{zpc} of the surface of raw saw dust

Batch kinetic and equilibrium studies :

A stock solution of Orange G was prepared by dissolving it in double distilled water. Experimental solutions of dye having known initial concentrations were prepared by diluting the stock solution. The pH of the experimental solutions was adjusted by adding different concentrations of 1 M HCl or NaOH solutions. About 50 mL of the experimental solutions was mixed with 1.0 g of adsorbent in a reagent bottle and the suspensions were equilibrated by shaking the reaction mixture at a fixed agitation speed (150 rpm), and temperature using a water bath shaker for a desired period of time. After equilibration, the supernatant liquids were filtered and separated from the solutions. The concentration of Orange G was determined using a double beam spectrophotometer (Systronics 2203)¹⁷ at λ_{max} 480 nm. Blank samples were also run under similar conditions of concentration.

The amount of adsorption at equilibrium, q_e (mg/g), was calculated by :

$$q_e = (C_o - C_e)V/W \quad (10)$$

$$\% \text{ removal} = 100 \times (C_o - C_e)/C_o \quad (11)$$

where C_o and C_e (mg/L) are the liquid-phase concentrations of dye initially and at equilibrium, respectively. V is the volume of the solution (L) and W is the mass of dry adsorbent used (g). The values expressed in the work are the average of three replications.

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